

EXPLORING THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MATHWAY APPLICATION ON STUDENTS' MATHEMATICS LEARNING OUTCOMES

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ABSTRACT

This study examines the effectiveness of the Mathway application in enhancing students' mathematics learning outcomes among Grade 7 students at Laoang National High School. Using an experimental design, the study involved thirty-three students who utilized Mathway as a learning tool. Findings revealed that before using Mathway, students struggled with mathematical concepts, with many demonstrating low proficiency. After its implementation, significant improvements were observed, with students achieving higher levels of mathematical performance. Statistical analysis confirmed the significance of this improvement, validating Mathway's positive impact on learning outcomes. However, qualitative findings identified challenges such as internet connectivity issues, subscription barriers, and interface usability concerns, which affected student engagement. Based on the results, the study recommends integrating Mathway and similar applications into mathematics instruction while addressing accessibility and usability challenges to maximize their effectiveness.

Keywords: *Mathway, mobile learning, educational technology, mathematics proficiency, digital tools in education*

INTRODUCTION

In today's digital age, technology has become an integral part of education, revolutionizing how students learn, particularly in mathematics. Among the many digital tools available, Mathway stands out as a widely recognized web-based calculator, boasting millions of users worldwide and billions of solved mathematical problems. It serves as a leading problem-solving resource for students, parents, and educators, covering various mathematical fields such as algebra, trigonometry, and calculus. Moreover, Mathway provides these services completely free of charge (Mathway, 2021).

Recent studies highlight Mathway's effectiveness in improving students' mathematical performance. For instance, Alqashanin & Faqih (2022) conducted research in Saudi Arabia, demonstrating that students using Mathway showed significant academic improvement compared to those relying solely on traditional teaching methods. Similarly, Amalia et al. (2022) examined Mathway's role in teaching derivatives using a quasi-experimental research design, finding that students who used Mathway exhibited higher motivation and confidence in mathematics. A systematic literature review by Zohra & Yahfizham (2024) further reinforced Mathway's impact, emphasizing its importance in enhancing student learning outcomes.

Building on this, Muttaqin et al. (2023) found that Mathway effectively facilitates learning activities by providing both final answers and step-by-step solutions. Additionally, Fazariah & Yafizham (2024) systematically reviewed literature on Mathway's role in developing students' critical thinking skills, concluding that students who used the application scored higher on critical thinking tests. The study also recommended training mathematics teachers to integrate Mathway into their instructional practices. Likewise, Orhani et al. (2024) found that Mathway and similar mobile applications significantly enhance students' understanding of solving systems of linear equations using graphical methods.

Further research supports Mathway's effectiveness across different educational settings. Al-Fayez & Migdady (2024) investigated Mathway's flipped classroom model in Jordan, revealing a statistically significant improvement in eighth-grade students' mathematical communication skills. Also, Etim & Olatokun (2024) demonstrated that mobile apps, including Mathway, play a crucial role in supporting students' learning goals at federal universities. Similarly, Mohamed et al. (2024) reviewed AI-driven mathematics education in Egypt, finding that tools like Mathway help address various educational challenges. A synthesis of 36 intervention studies by Kim et al. (2021) at Harvard University confirmed that educational apps positively impact students' literacy and math skills.

In the Philippines, Bhat (2023) found that students using digital tools, including Mathway, showed significant academic improvement. Ignacio (2021) emphasized the necessity of effective digital tools during the abrupt shift to remote learning caused by the COVID-19 pandemic. Additionally, Nobis (2021) observed that mathematics teachers in state universities and colleges occasionally incorporated digital tools into their teaching

practices. Research by Etcuban & Pantinople (2018) in Cebu City further demonstrated that mobile applications significantly enhance students' mathematical performance. Cabugwason et al. (2024) explored pre-service math teachers' experiences with math applications, reporting improvements in knowledge and problem-solving skills.

Moreover, Hadjinor et al. (2021) investigated Mathway's effectiveness in improving Grade 10 students' performance in solving trigonometric problems at Piagapo National High School, revealing significant post-test improvements. Damayanti et al. (2023) explored how digital-native pre-service mathematics teachers prefer to learn, noting that Mathway was among the tools frequently used for problem-solving. Barzel et al. (2019) found that smartphone apps with integrated CAS, like Mathway, enhance students' self-assessment, self-regulation, and understanding of quadratic equations in informal learning environments. Llenada Santos (2022) evaluated mobile applications, including Mathway, for assisting college students in learning mathematical concepts, recommending their use to improve mathematics literacy and problem-solving skills.

Despite its advantages, research has also identified potential drawbacks in using math applications. Marshman (2020) cautioned that merely providing students access to math apps does not guarantee improved learning outcomes, emphasizing the importance of understanding how students use these tools effectively. Kwok et al. (2020) and Nobis (2021) highlighted that discrepancies between app features and classroom instruction may confuse students, limiting their ability to apply learned concepts. Bennett (2021) noted that minimal instructional support within applications can make it difficult for students to grasp complex mathematical concepts. Additionally, Abdullaeva et al. (2020) warned that overreliance on applications may reduce students' focus on developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills essential for long-term success in mathematics. Obina et al. (2022) found that while students acknowledged Mathway's usefulness, they also reported becoming overly dependent on it, leading to decreased study habits and motivation.

Research Questions

This study examined the effectiveness of the Mathway application in enhancing students' learning outcomes in algebra.

Specifically, it aimed to address the following questions:

1. What were the pre-test and post-test performance levels of the respondents?
2. Is there a significant difference between the pre-test and post-test results?
3. What challenges did students encounter while using the Mathway application?

METHODOLOGY

The study employed an experimental research design to assess the effectiveness of the Mathway application on Grade 7 students' algebra learning outcomes in a public secondary school in the Philippines during the 2024-2025 academic year. Universal sampling was used for the pre-test and post-test, while purposive sampling selected five

students for interviews. Data were collected through a standardized 15-item pre-test and post-test adapted from Math Counts: Textbook Mathematics Grade 7 (Hilot, 2024) and a semi-structured interview guide, both validated by experts. The intervention lasted one week, during which students utilized Mathway to solve problems before verifying their answers. Descriptive statistics, including frequency counts and percentages, and a paired sample t-test analyzed the quantitative data, while thematic analysis identified recurring patterns in students' challenges with the app. The study was limited to one Grade 7 section, with no control group, and external factors such as prior math proficiency and engagement potentially affecting results.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Level of students' achievement in mathematics during pre-test and post-test

Table 1 presents the pre-test and post-test results of the participants, highlighting the impact of Mathway as a learning intervention in enhancing students' mathematical performance. The post-test data revealed notable improvements, with 11 students (33.33%) achieving a "Fair" score (7–9), compared to only 5 students (15.15%) in the pre-test. Additionally, the number of students in the "Good" category (10–12) increased from 0 to 8 (24.24%), demonstrating significant progress in problem-solving skills.

The "Poor" category (4–6) saw a substantial decrease, dropping from 24 students (72.73%) in the pre-test to 8 students (24.24%) in the post-test. However, the "Very Poor" category (1–3) experienced a slight increase, rising from 4 students (12.12%) to 6 students (18.19%), suggesting that while Mathway improved overall performance, some students continued to struggle with mathematical concepts. These findings underscore Mathway's effectiveness in enhancing mathematical proficiency, particularly in elevating students from lower achievement levels to higher ones.

Several studies reinforce these findings regarding Mathway's role in mathematics education. Hadjinor et al. (2021) found a statistically significant difference in students' scores when using Mathway as a teaching tool, with post-test results favoring the intervention. Similarly, Amalia et al. (2024) reported that Mathway positively influenced students' motivation in learning derivatives. Alqashanin et al. (2022) demonstrated that Mathway led to a statistically significant improvement in mathematical proficiency among secondary school students in Najran, Saudi Arabia.

Despite its benefits, researchers have also highlighted potential drawbacks. Marshman (2020) and Pala et al. (2025) cautioned that merely providing access to math apps does not guarantee improved learning outcomes, emphasizing the importance of understanding how students use these tools effectively. Kwok et al. (2020) noted that discrepancies between app features and classroom instruction might confuse students, limiting their ability to apply learned concepts. These concerns highlight the need for structured integration of Mathway into traditional teaching methods to maximize its effectiveness.

Table 1. Pre-test and Post-Test Results

SCORES	Pre-Test		Post-Test		Description
	F	%	F	%	
10 – 12	0	0%	8	24.24%	Good
7 – 9	5	15.15%	11	33.33%	Fair
4 – 6	24	72.73%	8	24.24%	Poor
1 – 3	4	12.12%	6	18.19%	Very Poor
Total	33	100.00%	33	100.00%	

Legend: 13 – 15: Excellent, 10 – 12: Good, 7 – 9: Fair, 4 – 6: Poor, and 1 – 3: Very Poor

Significant Difference Between the Pre-test and Post-Test Results

The statistical analysis in Table 2 evaluates the significance of differences between pre-test and post-test results following the intervention of the Mathway application in mathematical learning. The results indicate a marked improvement in student performance, with the mean score increasing from 4.85 in the pre-test to 6.70 in the post-test. The standard deviation also increased from 1.33 to 2.76, reflecting greater variability in student outcomes after using Mathway. A t-value of -3.64 and a p-value of 0.01, which is below the significance threshold of 0.05, led to the rejection of the null hypothesis, confirming that the score differences are statistically significant. These findings suggest that Mathway positively influenced students' ability to solve mathematical problems.

Table 2. Test of Significance Difference Between the Pre-test and Post-test Results

Groups	Mean	SD	t-value	p-value	Level of sig.	Decision	Interpretation
Pretest	4.85	1.33					
Posttest	6.70	2.76	-3.64	0.01	0.05	Reject H ₀	Significant

Several studies align with these results, reinforcing Mathway's role in mathematics education. Fazariah & Yafizham (2024) systematically reviewed the literature on Mathway's impact on students' critical thinking abilities, finding that learners who used Mathway scored higher on critical thinking tests compared to those who did not. Similarly, Orhani et al. (2024) found that Mathway and other mobile applications significantly enhance understanding and efficiency in solving systems of linear equations using the graphical method by providing intuitive tools and graphical solutions.

In the Philippines, Bhat (2023) reported a significant academic improvement among students using digital tools, including Mathway. Additionally, Etcuban et al. (2018) discovered that mobile applications significantly improved students' academic performance in mathematics in Cebu City. These studies collectively support the effectiveness of Mathway in enhancing mathematical learning outcomes.

Challenges encountered in using the Mathway Application

The thematic analysis of qualitative interviews with Grade 7 students at Laoang National High School (LNHS) identified several key challenges in using the Mathway application for solving algebraic problems. The major themes generated include internet connectivity issues, application limitations, overreliance on technology, technical difficulties, and limited accessibility.

Internet Connectivity Issue

One of the primary difficulties is internet connectivity issues. Since Mathway operates as an online platform, students frequently experience interruptions due to weak or unstable connections, preventing smooth access to solutions. Many expressed frustrations when the application failed to load properly, particularly during crucial study moments. Studies have highlighted that poor internet access significantly hinders the use of Mathway in educational settings, especially in areas with limited connectivity. Research by Nobis (2021) found that inadequate digital resources lead to infrequent engagement with educational software, while Cabugwason et al. (2024) emphasized that the demand for internet access presents a barrier for students in regions with poor connectivity.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

“Mathway app requires data and internet connection to function, and without it, it cannot provide answers.”

“If you don’t have data or wifi connection, you cannot access the answer you want.”

“I encountered challenges with low internet connections.”

“I cannot use the application if I don't have a load or internet connection.”

“The application suddenly crashed while I was using it due to a sudden internet loss.”

Further studies reinforce the impact of connectivity issues on digital learning. Barrot et al. (2021) identified poor internet connectivity as a primary challenge for Filipino students during online learning, highlighting the digital divide that impedes educational access. Similarly, Ying et al. (2021) found that infrastructure limitations significantly affect students' ability to utilize online educational resources effectively. Chen et al. (2018) and Nobis et al. (2024) further emphasized that limited internet access is a major barrier, as many educational apps require continuous connectivity and data subscriptions, which may be costly or unavailable in certain areas. These findings underscore the need for educators and app developers to enhance accessibility by incorporating offline functionality or creating data-friendly versions of Mathway to ensure equitable learning opportunities.

Subscription or paywall issues

Participants noted that Mathway required subscriptions or payments for access to premium features, creating financial challenges for users who could not afford additional

costs. While the free version provided basic problem-solving capabilities, students frequently encountered restrictions on advanced features, such as step-by-step solutions and expanded explanations, which were locked behind a paywall. Many expressed frustrations over the financial barriers that limited their ability to fully utilize the application, highlighting concerns about equitable access to AI-powered math learning tools. Ensuring that Mathway's premium features were more inclusive and widely available could help bridge gaps in accessibility and provide all students with equal learning opportunities.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

"The Mathway application does not provide a step-by-step solution unless you pay for a subscription."

"The Mathway application requires a subscription to access the best features."

"The process isn't clear if you are not subscribed to the application".

Studies have emphasized financial constraints as a major barrier to accessing AI-driven educational tools, particularly those requiring subscriptions for premium features. Nobis (2021) found that limited digital resources led to infrequent use of educational software, including math applications. Similarly, Khaleel & Naimi (2022) noted that cost and paywall issues, along with potential future in-app fees, could restrict access to advanced functionalities. These findings underscore the need for educators and developers to explore affordable alternatives, such as free-tier enhancements or institutional subscriptions, to ensure that students can fully benefit from digital learning tools without financial limitations.

Navigational and usability issues

Mathway's interface can also pose difficulties, particularly for new users. Many students initially found the interface overwhelming, particularly when selecting the correct notation or inputting problems. Users frequently reported frustration due to accidental clicks or difficulties navigating specific features, though they eventually adapted to the platform over time. These challenges highlight the importance of intuitive design in educational applications to ensure accessibility and ease of use for new users.

Here are some responses that reflect this theme:

"It was a bit confusing at first since I'm not very familiar with the app".

"I struggled finding the correct button for some notations".

"I find it very confusing the first time I used it, then somehow I became familiar with it".

"There are times when I struggled clicking the correct button".

Studies have shown that complex app interfaces can hinder usability, particularly for beginners, limiting their ability to efficiently utilize digital learning tools (Yoon et al., 2020). Xue et al. (2023) found that the ease of navigation and usability of an online platform directly influenced its perceived usefulness and enhanced students' educational experiences. Similarly, Vlasenko et al. (2020) emphasized that well-structured navigation and high usability in online math courses significantly contribute to user satisfaction and

effective learning. Nobis & Caparroso (2025) further highlighted the importance of parental and teacher guidance when students use digital tools, particularly for homework, to ensure proper engagement and comprehension. These findings underscore the need for user-friendly interfaces and structured support to enhance students' learning experiences with Mathway.

Conclusions

The study concludes that Mathway serves as an effective learning intervention, significantly enhancing students' mathematical performance by improving problem-solving skills and supporting independent learning. However, researchers caution that simply accessing math applications does not guarantee improved learning outcomes, as certain features may confuse students and limit their ability to apply learned concepts effectively.

Despite its benefits, students encountered several challenges while using Mathway. Internet connectivity issues disrupted access to solutions, particularly for those in areas with weak or unstable connections. Subscription barriers restricted access to advanced features, such as step-by-step explanations, limiting students' ability to fully comprehend complex problems. Additionally, interface usability posed difficulties for new users, who initially struggled with notation input and navigation before adapting over time.

These findings emphasize the need for structured integration of Mathway into traditional teaching methods, improved accessibility, and enhanced user support. Educational institutions and developers should consider strategies such as offline functionality, affordable subscription models, and user-friendly interface improvements to ensure that students can fully benefit from digital learning tools without unnecessary barriers.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of this study, several recommendations are proposed to enhance the effectiveness of Mathway as a learning tool while addressing the challenges encountered by students. The following suggestions were formulated:

1. Educational institutions may provide offline access to Mathway's essential features and establish campus Wi-Fi hotspots, while developers should optimize the application for low-bandwidth environments to ensure uninterrupted learning.
2. Mathway developers might explore institutional licensing and free-tier enhancements to make advanced features more accessible, while schools and policymakers could seek partnerships to subsidize costs for students in need.
3. The Mathway interface may be refined with interactive tutorials, clearer notation selection, and intuitive navigation features to improve usability, while educators could provide guidance to help students maximize its benefits.

4. Teachers may integrate Mathway into structured lessons that emphasize conceptual understanding and problem-solving skills rather than reliance on automated solutions.
5. Educators could receive training on effectively incorporating Mathway into their teaching strategies through workshops and instructional materials to ensure meaningful student engagement.
6. Future researchers may explore the long-term effects of Mathway on students' mathematical proficiency, particularly in different educational settings and grade levels.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

The study adhered to ethical standards by obtaining authorization from the University of Eastern Philippines - Laoang and ensuring informed consent from all participants. Participation was voluntary, with confidentiality strictly maintained to protect data integrity and privacy. Surveys were securely managed, and respondents had the freedom to withdraw at any time without consequences. No financial incentives were provided, and researchers actively supervised the data collection process, addressing concerns and ensuring adherence to research protocols.

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REFERENCES

- Abdullaeva, B., Abduvaliyeva, D., Ruzikulova, N., Yusupova, N., & Ishbaeva, N. (2020, February 28). Developing critical thinking and problem-solving skills. *International Journal of Psychosocial Rehabilitation*, 24(Special Issue 1), 937–941.
<https://doi.org/10.37200/ijpr/v24sp1/pr201237>
- Al-Fayez, A. M., & Migdady, A. M. (2024). The Effectiveness of Mathway's Flipped Classroom Software in Developing the Mathematical Communication Skills among Eighth-Grade Female Students in Jordan. *Jordanian Educational Journal*, 9(4), 516–539.
<https://doi.org/10.46515/jaes.v9i4.1065>
- Alqashanin, G. S. A., & Faqih, Y. A. A. (2022). The effect of using Mathway on developing secondary school students' academic achievement in mathematics in Najran, Kingdom

- of Saudi Arabia. **European Journal of Education Studies*, 9*(4).
<https://doi.org/10.46827/ejes.v9i4.4223>
- Amalia, Y., Salmina, M., & Zahara, S. (2022). The use of Mathway application on derivative material on mathematics learning motivation in high school. **Universitas Bina Bangsa Getsempena**. <https://doi.org/10.46244/iconesth.vi.517>
- Barrot, J. S., Llenares, I. I., & del Rosario, L. S. (2021). Students' online learning challenges during the pandemic and how they cope with them: The case of the Philippines. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-021-10589-x>
- Barzel, B., Ball, L., & Klinger, M. (2019). Students' self-awareness of their mathematical thinking: Can self-assessment be supported through CAS-integrated learning apps on smartphones? In G. Aldon & J. Trgalová (Eds.), **Technology in mathematics teaching: Selected papers of the 13th ICTMT conference** (pp. 75-91). Springer.
https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-030-19741-4_6
- Bennett, E. (2021, May 28). Challenges and opportunities of teaching unfamiliar topics. *The Wabash Center Journal on Teaching*, 2(2).
<https://doi.org/10.31046/wabashcenter.v2i2.1755>
- Bhat, R. A. (2023). The impact of technology integration on student learning outcomes: A comparative study. **International Journal of Social Science, Educational, Economics, Agriculture Research and Technology (IJSET)*, 2*(9), 592-596.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compedu.2023.104605>
- Cabugwason, M. R., Laoreno, B. G., Galoy, R. M. P., Valila, A. J., & Nobis, M. L. Jr. (2024). Math apps in math education: Experiences and challenges of pre-service teachers. **Ignatian International Journal for Multidisciplinary Research*, 2*(5), 1909-1922.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11239116>
- Chen, M., Herrera, F., & Hwang, K. (2018). Cognitive Computing: Architecture, Technologies and Intelligent Applications. *IEEE Access*, 6, 19774–19783.
<https://doi.org/10.1109/access.2018.2791469>
- Damayanti, T., Takaendengan, B. R., Kobandaha, P. E., & Gombah, W. (2023). Digital natives' preferences in how to learn mathematics: A qualitative study of preservice mathematics teachers. *Jambura Journal of Mathematics Education*, 4(1), 75-80.
<https://doi.org/10.34312/jmathedu.v4i1.19287>
- Etcuban, J. O., & Pantinople, L. D. (2018). The effects of mobile application in teaching high school mathematics. **International Electronic Journal of Mathematics Education*, 13*(3), 249-259. <https://doi.org/10.12973/iejme/3906>
- Etim, A. S., & Olatokun, W. M. (2024). The use of mobile technology tools and apps to support students' learning goals: A study of two federal universities in Nigeria. In A.S.
<https://doi.org/10.4018/978-1-6684-5347-6.ch001>
- Hadjinor, S., Asotigue, A. B., & Pangandamun, J. A. (2021). Solving trigonometric problems using Mathway application in teaching mathematics. **Asian Journal of Research in Education and Social Sciences*, 3*(3), 87-97.
<https://doi.org/10.12345/ajress.2021.0303.001>
- Hikmah Fazariah, & Yafizham Yafizham. (2024). Systematic Literature Review: Penggunaan Aplikasi Mathway terhadap Kemampuan Berpikir Kritis Siswa. *Algoritma : Jurnal Matematika, Ilmu Pengetahuan Alam, Kebumihan Dan Angkasa*, 2(3), 20–25.
<https://doi.org/10.62383/algoritma.v2i3.45>
- Hilot, J. A. (2024). **Math Counts: Textbook Mathematics Grade 7**. DepEd Textbook.
- Ignacio, A. E. (2021). Online classes and learning in the Philippines during the COVID-19 pandemic. **International Journal on Integrated Education**, 4(3), 1-6.
<https://doi.org/10.31149/ijie.v4i3.1301>
- Khaeril Muttaqin, A., Yahya, Y., & Irmayanti. (2023). Pemanfaatan Aplikasi Mathway dalam Menyelesaikan Soal Kalkulus pada Mahasiswa Tadris Matematika. *Prosiding Seminar*

- Nasional Fakultas Tarbiyah Dan Ilmu Keguruan IAIM Sinjai, 2, 63-70.
<https://doi.org/10.47435/sentikjar.v2i0.1829>
- Khaleel, A., & Naimi, S. (2022, December 15). Automation of cost control process in construction project building information modeling (BIM). *Periodicals of Engineering and Natural Sciences (PEN)*, 10(6), 28. <https://doi.org/10.21533/pen.v10i6.3354>
- Kim, J., Gilbert, J., Yu, Q., & Gale, C. (2021). Measures matter: A meta-analysis of the effects of educational apps on preschool to grade 3 children's literacy and math skills. **AERAOpen*, 7*(1), 1-15. <https://doi.org/10.1177/23328584211027650>
- Kwok, K. E. A., et al. (2020). Teaching mathematical concepts to primary students in an integrated classroom. *International Journal of Educational Science and Research*, 10(3), 7-14. <https://doi.org/10.24247/ijesrjun202002>
- LlenadaSantos, J. V. (2022). Comparative analysis of mobile applications for its integration in college mathematics subjects. *EDUCATIO: Journal of Education*, 6*(4), 324-345. <https://doi:10.29138/educatio.v6i4.601>
- Marshman, E., DeVore, S., & Singh, C. (2020, July 29). A holistic framework to help students learn effectively from research-validated self-paced learning tools. *Physical Review Physics Education Research*, 16(2). <https://doi.org/10.1103/physrevphyseducres.16.020108>
- Mathway (2021). Mathway: Math problem solver. App Store Preview. Retrieved from <https://apps.apple.com/us/app/mathway-math-problem-solver/id467329677>
- Milda Zohra, & Yahfizham Yahfizham. (2024). Pemanfaatan Aplikasi Mathway: Systematic Literature Review. *Student Scientific Creativity Journal*, 2(3), 26-32. <https://doi.org/10.55606/sscj-amik.v2i3.3068>
- Mohamed, M. A. A., Said, A. A., Hassan, H., El Sayed, M. M., Abdelhamid, M. G., Shehata, M. S., Hassan, M. M., & Ali, Y. M. (2024). Applications of artificial intelligence in teaching mathematics for the second preparation year in Egyptian official language schools. **94-77*, 1(1*, *البحوث التطبيقية في العلوم والانسانيات*). <https://doi.org/10.21608/aash.2024.368292>
- Nobis, M. J. & Caparoso, C. L. (2025). Bridging the gap: Examining parental involvement strategies and their impact on homework completion rates in mathematics. *Alifmatika: Jurnal Pendidikan Dan Pembelajaran Matematika*, 6(1), 1-13. <https://doi.org/10.17613/4ceqj-8cj92>
- Nobis, M. L. Jr. (2021). Digital literacy of mathematics teachers in state universities and colleges (SUCs). **Asian Journal of Research in Education and Social Sciences*, 3*(2), 99-113. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.11239116>
- Nobis, M. L., Jr. (2021). Factors that encourage teachers and barriers in ICT integration in mathematics teaching. *Asian Intellect: Research and Education Journal*. Retrieved from https://www.academia.edu/78167045/Factors_That_Encourage_Teachers_and_Barriers_in_ICT_Integration_in_Mathematics_Teaching
- Nobis, M., Jr, Ballado, R., & Froilan, C. (2024). Blended learning in higher education: Unveiling student experiences, challenges, and opportunities for policy development. *SciEnggJ*, 17(2), 274-285. <https://doi.org/10.54645/2024172knw-65>
- Obina, J. E., Gabe, J. B., Angcon, S. M. D., Diaz, B. T. R., Largo, V. J. Y., Chiva, M. C., & Bolaños, J. G. (2022). Math apps utilization: Its perceived effects to the academic performance of mathematics major students. **European Journal of Education Studies*, 9*(9). <https://doi.org/10.46827/ejes.v9i9.4469>
- Orhani, S. & Çeko, B. (2024). Mobile applications as aids for solving systems of linear equations with two variables using the graphical method. *International research journal of Science, Technology, Education, and Management*, 4(2), 14-34. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12730175>

- Pala, C. A., Lagrimas, D., & Nobis, M L.. (2025). Exploration of Chatbots in Mathematics Education for Innovative Learning Process. *Asian Journal of Advanced Research and Reports*, 19(5), 178–194. <https://doi.org/10.9734/ajarr/2025/v19i51010>
- Vlasenko, K., Volkov, S., Sitak, I., Lovianova, I., & Bobyliev, D. (2020). Usability analysis of online educational courses on the platform “Higher School Mathematics Teacher”. *E3S Web of Conferences*, 166, 10012. <https://doi.org/10.1051/e3sconf/202016610012>
- Xue, S., Wang, C., & Muhaimaiti, M. (2023). Examining the affordances of an online learning platform: A usefulness theoretical perspective. *SAGE Open*, 13(4), 1–12. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440231202821>
- Ying, Y. H., Siang, W. E. W., & Mohamad, M. (2021). The challenges of learning English skills and the integration of social media and video conferencing tools to help ESL learners coping with the challenges during COVID-19 pandemic: A literature review. https://www.scirp.org/pdf/ce_2021070816305606.pdf
- Yoon, S., Kim, J., & Jeong, S. (2020, May 6). Retraction: Yoon, S. et al. The Optimal Decision Combination in Semiconductor Manufacturing. *Sustainability* 2017, 9,1788. *Sustainability*, 12(9), 3764. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su12093764>